

THE ISSUE OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN ENGAGEMENT IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8432718>

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Abstract

The article discusses the rules and procedures for conducting physical education training in educational institutions.

Keywords

Education, body, body, health, time, training.

Physical education of young people (children) engaged in educational institutions (preschool educational institutions, secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges) is considered to be the main part of the physical education system of Uzbekistan. This is the largest section, in which students (children) are expected to continue their knowledge, experience and movement skills in preschool, general education school and academic lyceum or vocational college, so during these years, they have important physical education activities. In the conditions of scientific and technical development, the work tasks of people are changing. In this case, physical work decreases and mental work increases. Therefore, the demand for physical fitness is increasing. Nowadays, in the newspaper pages, medical workers are talking about "hypodynamia", that is, they are worried about the fact that physical exercises, physical work, and active movement are decreasing day by day in human activities. This, in turn, is the cause of the annual increase in cardiovascular disease, the disease of the century. According to doctors, one of the necessary means of prevention of this disease is more movement and exercise, and it is of great importance to be able to effectively use the "healing forces of nature". Improving physical education in educational institutions is a component of improving educational work, and the Law "On Physical Education and Sports" (January 14, 1992), the Perspective Program "For a Healthy Generation" (1993), the Law "On Education" and "National personnel training program" (August 29, 1997), It contributes to the fulfillment of the requirements of the decree "On the establishment of the Children's Sports

Development Fund of Uzbekistan" (October 27, 2002). In recent years, it has become known that there are serious deficiencies in the physical development of students (children) in educational institutions, and they do not know the genetic rules necessary for the life of students (children), and they do not have enough knowledge in the field of first aid. There are various forms of physical education in educational institutions. Unfortunately, in places (pre-school educational institutions, secondary schools (primary, secondary), academic lyceums or vocational colleges, it is limited to the organization and conduct of classes. This does not satisfy the demands of students (children) for movement. Pedagogical observations show that in the course of physical education classes, students (children) get the least amount of movement activity necessary for life. According to the order of the Ministry of Public Education of Uzbekistan dated January 30, 1989 No. 45, it was planned to have 3 hours of physical education classes per week. But physical education teachers could not use it effectively. In addition, the lack of methodologically correct organization of classes (non-specialist teachers organize and conduct physical education classes with elementary school students in most kindergartens with children): as a result of the selection of exercises taking into account the age characteristics and physical development of students, the training of physical qualities in students, the formation of movement skills not enough.

As a result, the physical behavior and activeness of the participants rapidly decreased. One of the strategic tasks of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan is to raise a physically healthy and spiritually mature person who is ready to do all good deeds in the future. In order to fulfill these tasks, it is emphasized that we need to have a new and creative approach to the planning and effective implementation of educational work, and to approach the work with initiative. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the system of physical education of pre-school and school-aged children, as well as academic lyceum, vocational college teenagers, to develop measures to improve their movement skills. In the upbringing of preschool and school-age children, adolescents and teenagers, they should be physically fit, Physical education plays a leading role in their mental development. The main place in solving these problems is the formation of a healthy lifestyle among children and adults, among teachers and parents, teaching genetic rules and requirements. Therefore, the first task is to help children develop fully, strengthen their health, prepare them for life, prepare them for useful work, and contribute to becoming a mature person. The use of various forms of physical education of students (children) in kindergarten and school is not only the task of physical education specialist and teacher, but also the direct task of educators and primary

school teachers, kindergarten, school community and school youth association activists. But in many educational institutions, physical education is not organized according to the state program. The first reason is that all those responsible for the physical education of schoolchildren do not have enough knowledge of the theory and methodology of physical education. There are very few methodological literature and manuals aimed at solving these problems. We attach great importance to the important role of the family in the strengthening of the social foundations of our republic, its stability, and the upbringing of a physically healthy, spiritually mature young generation, on which the future fate of our country depends, and we consider it a pleasure to contribute to its implementation. Theory and methodology of physical education as an educational subject. Theory of physical education (general principles) physical education as an educational subject, is considered the main subject in the training of specialists in physical culture and sports, as well as in obtaining special knowledge and information. In the curricula of the physical education faculties of the State Institute of Physical Education of Uzbekistan, the Regional Pedagogical Institute and Universities, the subject of physical education provides a full system of knowledge of the theory of physical education and sports. Some types of theoretical and methodological sections are studied. Physical education is related to social phenomena. To characterize these phenomena, the reasons for the origin of physical education, its place in the life of society: the historical character of physical education: the class purpose of physical education in society:

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